

Exposing the Blind Spot: A Real-Time Clinical Audit Benchmarking Emergency Care Plans in Vulnerable Patients Against an Expert-Informed Model

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1. Introduction

Emergency care plans are intended to protect the most clinically vulnerable patients during moments of crisis. They are documents that highlight patient wishes or preferences in the event of an emergency. However, longstanding

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concerns persist regarding the clarity, actionability, and legal robustness of these plans in real-world clinical settings.

On 22nd of May 2025, following a discussion with a leading academic voice in end-of-life care, the author was inspired to initiate a live clinical audit to examine the quality of emergency care plans encountered during routine out-of-hours work. This discussion highlighted the need to provide documented evidence that existing emergency health care planning was unclear and inactionable. The author has seen and reviewed thousands of emergency care plans over the previous two years of clinical practice, noting they are often vague, inactionable and impeded rather than supported clinical decision making, both in and out of hours in community care settings (primary care, urgent care).

The aim was to benchmark current practice against a structured, expert-informed planning model developed by the author. This model is grounded in nearly a decade of cross-specialty frontline experience and has been refined over seven years. A separately published narrative audit describing the early success of this model includes a foreword by Professor Max Watson (Consultant in Palliative Medicine, Omagh; Associate Professor, St. John's National Academy; and Director, Project ECHO Hospice UK).

While national guidelines, including NICE NG97 and NG142, outline clear expectations for personalised care planning, capacity assessment, and family involvement, this audit found these principles were often absent or inconsistently applied in real-world documentation.

To the author's knowledge, this is the first UK-based real-time audit of emergency healthcare plans conducted during clinical hours across a wide geographic area, focusing on care home residents, cognitively impaired individuals, and housebound patients. The audit evaluated the presence, specificity, legal integrity, ethical standards, and clinical usability of existing documentation.

While the author's prior clinical experience had suggested that many emergency care plans were vague or inactionable, this audit also revealed more serious and unexpected findings: potentially significant and systemic ethical and legal shortcomings, particularly among patients with dementia. These findings raise urgent questions about the alignment of current planning practices with both the Mental Capacity Act and safe, person-centred clinical decision-making.

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Disclaimer:

This paper is for informational purposes only and does not constitute medical or legal advice. All clinical decisions should be made in line with local protocols and professional guidance. All data has been anonymised. No patient care was compromised during the audit process. This paper presents early findings and should not be used to guide care without further evaluation or training.

2. Methods

Audit Design and Clinical Context:

A live clinical audit was conducted personally by the author over six urgent care shifts, totalling **72 clinical hours** between **22 May 2025 at 23:00** and **1 June 2025 at 08:00** (a 10-day period). Shifts included **telephone triage, face-to-face clinic reviews, and home visits** to care homes and private residences, spanning both North and South Cumbria.

Inclusion Criteria (Vulnerable Patients - frail and cognitive impairment adults):

Patients were included if they met any of the following:

- Residing in a care home
- Classified as housebound
- Diagnosed with dementia or documented cognitive impairment

Exclusion Criteria:

Vulnerable adults were excluded if:

- Their general practice records were not accessible for a minimum of 12 months (required to identify emergency care planning activity)

Data Collection Process:

Out of 270 total patients reviewed during 72 hours of clinical work, 72 met the inclusion criteria. One was excluded due to inaccessible medical records, leaving 71 patients in the final analysis. Data was collected during live clinical care and, where feasible, recorded in real time, typically during waiting periods between call

handling or home visits. Full data entry and plan scoring were completed post-shift or during clinically quiet periods, ensuring that patient care was never compromised and that accuracy was preserved.

Audit Tool Criteria:

Each patient's emergency care plan was assessed using a structured tool, evaluating:

Plan Specificity Score (0–3):

- **0** = No plan
- **1** = Vague or blanket guidance (e.g., “for escalation if needed,” “prefers not to be admitted,” “not for escalation”)
- **2** = Some actionable detail but lacking scenario-specificity
- **3** = Robust, scenario-specific plan with clear, clinically useful escalation pathways

Plan Actionability Score (0-5):

Calculated by summing binary “Yes/No” criteria (excluding specificity score - below) for legal and clinical completeness.

- Whether the plan was clearly coded and easily visible in records (Y/N)
- Discussion Involvement of Next of Kin (NOK), Power Of Attorney (POA) or Independent Mental Capacity Advocate (IMCA) (Y/N)
- Documentation of capacity assessment or best interest process (Y/N)
- Whether the plan was up-to-date (within past 12 months) (Y/N)
- Presence of a DNACPR (Y/N)

Ethical Considerations:

This audit was conducted within the scope of clinical governance as a quality improvement initiative. All data was anonymised following collection. Patients were reviewed as part of routine clinical care, and clinical needs always took precedence. The scale of the audit, **72 vulnerable patients out of 270 total reviewed (26.6%)**, reflects the breadth and diversity of patients presenting in real-world urgent care settings.

3. Results

Patient Characteristics:

- Total patients reviewed: **270**
- Vulnerable patients meeting inclusion criteria: **72**
- Patients excluded due to inaccessible records: **1**
- **Final audit sample: 71 patients**
- Gender split: **37 male, 34 female**
- Age range: **58–100 years** (mean age: **83**)

Setting Representation:

Patients were registered with **over 30 general practices** and associated with **more than 25 care homes** across North and South Cumbria. **46 patients** living in care homes, **19 patients** were housebound. A total of **38 cognitively impaired or dementia patients** were represented across all settings.

Plan Specificity Findings (Score 0-3):

Emergency Plans For Vulnerable Patients (n = 71)	Total Number of Patients	Total Inactionable Plans (score 1)	Total Actionable Plans (score 2)	Total Robust Plans (score 3)
Emergency Plan Present	41 (58%)	38/41 (93%)	3/41 (7%)	0/41 (0%)
Emergency Plan Absent	30 (42%)	-	-	-

- **3/41 (7%)** of patients **somewhat actionable emergency care plans** (score = 2)

- “One was **out-of-dated** (last reviewed over a year ago)”
 - “One lacked **clear visibility, no capacity assessment, and no NOK involvement**”
 - “One was created **on behalf of a dementia patient** without discussion with the patient, **NOK**, or **IMCA**, potentially breaching the **Mental Capacity Act**”
- **0/71 (0%) of patients had robust, scenario-specific plans (score = 3)**

In Summary: 68/71 (96%) of the vulnerable patients audited had **no usable emergency care plan** to support emergency decision making. Of the **3/71 (4%)** plans that did provide some guidance - issues exist with them being out-of-date or having legal and/or ethical concerns.

Plan Actionability Findings (Score 0-5):

Actionability Scoring for Emergency Care Plans (n = 41)	Plan Clearly Coded and Visible? (Y/N)	Discussion Involvement with NOK, POA, or IMCA Documented? (Y/N)	Capacity or Best Interest Decision Clearly Documented? (Y/N)	Plan Up-to-Date (within 1 year)? (Y/N)	DNACPR Present? (Y/N)
Yes	14 (34%)	12 (29%)	13 (32%)	28 (68%)	28 (68%)
No	27 (66%)	29 (71%)	28 (68%)	13 (32%)	13 (32%)

- **Only 2/71 (3%) of patient score 5/5**
- **On average plans scored 2.5/5 for actionability**

In Summary: Despite clinical and legal completeness for only **2 (3%)** plans total, both of those emergency plans score 1 (inactionable). This highlights that even robust planning still results in inactionable plans. The vast majority of plans appeared to lack the legal, ethical, and review standards required to instill trust in the clinicians using them.

Key Clinical Insight:

Multiple patients in this audit avoided hospital admission, yet none of these outcomes were attributable to existing emergency care plans. In one illustrative case, a dementia patient with a previously traumatic hospital experience was managed safely in the community during an out-of-hours triage call. This was made possible through real-time contact with multiple individuals, including next of kin, and a clear understanding of the patient's wishes. The decision which honoured patient dignity and prevented further harm was made not on the basis of documented guidance, but through the author's clinical expertise and proactive advocacy.

Ethical and Legal Concerns in Dementia Subgroup (n = 38):

Dementia Subgroup Plan Specificity Findings (Score 0-3):

Emergency Plans For Dementia Patient Subgroup (n = 38)	Total Number of Patients	Total Inactionable Plans (score 1)	Total Actionable Plans (score 2)	Total Robust Plans (score 3)
Emergency Plan Present	25 (66%)	24/25 (96%)	1/25 (4%)	0/25 (0%)
Emergency Plan Absent	13 (34%)	-	-	-

- **Only 4/25 (16%) had BOTH capacity-assessed and involvement with a next of kin**
- **10/25 (40%) LACKED both capacity assessment and NOK, POA, or IMCA involvement**
- **6/25 (24%) involved NOK but had no documented capacity assessment**

- **5/25 (20%)** documented **capacity**, but did **not involve a NOK, POA or IMCA**

In Summary: 21/25 (84%) of emergency care plans for patients with dementia raised **serious ethical or legal concerns**.

In one case, a plan was created without input from a communicative dementia patient, raising potential concerns about compliance with the Mental Capacity Act.

4. Discussion

This audit represents one of the first known real-time, clinician-led evaluations of emergency care planning for vulnerable patients conducted during live out-of-hours clinical work. With 270 total patients reviewed across six urgent care shifts and 71 meeting predefined vulnerability criteria the audit provides a rare, real-world snapshot of emergency healthcare plan quality in the UK.

A key advantage of conducting a live audit in real time is the ability to capture not only the content of emergency care documentation, but its accessibility and usability during actual clinical decision-making. Unlike retrospective audits, which may benefit from ample review time and static data sets, a real-time audit reflects the conditions under which urgent decisions are made, including time pressure, incomplete information. Accessing and evaluating patient records during live triage, face to face encounters and home visits offers a clearer picture of how documentation either supports or hinders safe care in practice.

This approach also enables faster insights and feedback than many traditional research methods, which can take months to coordinate, extract, and analyse data. By embedding evaluation directly into clinical practice, a live audit offers both immediacy and authenticity, revealing the system as it is, not as it is theorised to be.

Findings of this audit were stark: 96% of emergency care plans were either absent or clinically inactionable. Of the 4% deemed somewhat actionable, none met the full criteria for clarity, ethical soundness, or legal compliance. Particularly

concerning were findings within the dementia subgroup, where over 80% of plans put in place lacked documented capacity assessments or advocate involvement. Several cases appeared to directly breach the Mental Capacity Act.

These patterns do not suggest isolated lapses but instead point to a systemic breakdown in emergency care planning for vulnerable patients. Despite national guidelines such as NICE NG97 and NG142, which mandate personalised, scenario-specific emergency care planning with clear legal and clinical standards, this audit reveals widespread non-adherence. Plans were often vague, outdated, hard to locate, and written without adequate clinical specificity or ethical due process.

Importantly, the root cause may be due to systemic limitations: workforce pressures, insufficient training, lack of standardisation, and lack of multi-disciplinary clinical expertise in delivery. Without formalised, accountable standards delivered by expert clinicians, vulnerable patients are left unsupported during urgent, time-sensitive crises.

During the audit, several hospital admissions were successfully prevented not due to existing emergency care plans, but through the author's clinical judgment, compassionate advocacy, and real-time communication with care teams and families. In similar scenarios, other clinicians may reasonably default to hospital admission as the perceived safer option, particularly in the absence of clear documentation or guidance. This highlights a critical gap between documentation and delivery: patients are not protected by the system itself, but by the variable presence of individual clinical skill and advocacy.

These findings suggest that when emergency care plans are absent, insufficiently actionable, and/or ethically and legally noncompliant, they are unable to support clinical decision-making and do not enable hospital admission avoidance. Plans may even undermine clinical decision-making rather than support it. In such cases, clinicians may face greater uncertainty and risk when plans exist but are not fit for purpose, highlighting the urgent need for higher standards, training, and accountability in emergency care planning.

While these results are deeply concerning, they are not without precedent. Existing literature has long called for reform in advance and emergency care planning. What sets this audit apart is its method: it measured what was actually present or absent at the point of care, in real time, across multiple clinical settings.

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This audit highlights not only a failure of systems and documentation, but also a compelling opportunity: to professionalise emergency care planning as a distinct, expert-led discipline, one that ensures clinical, legal, and human standards are met for patients in a vulnerable state. The author's refined model of expert and early second-cycle audit data suggest clinical expertise and improvements in emergency care planning documentation may support a better way forward.

Limitations

This audit was conducted over a 10-day period during live clinical shifts, without funding or formal academic support. The audit was limited to Cumbria, though it included patients from over 30 GP practices and 25 care homes, many involving professionals with national training experience. The audit, analysis, and full paper were completed by a single clinician within a 10-day period. While this speed is uncommon, it enabled rapid, grounded reflection, it also underscores the need for larger, collaborative studies to validate and expand on these findings.

5. Conclusion

This audit raises significant ethical, legal, and clinical concerns. Current emergency care planning practices may contribute to avoidable hospital admissions, undermine patient autonomy, and erode clinician trust in documentation during critical decision-making.

The findings underscore an urgent need for systemic improvement with three key recommendations:

- The development of structured, expert-led emergency care planning as a recognised clinical discipline
- National training and certification to ensure legal, ethical, and clinical standards are consistently met

- Routine auditing of planning quality, visibility, and compliance with frameworks such as the Mental Capacity Act and NICE guidance

Improving the clarity, actionability, and integrity of emergency care plans is essential — not only for safer clinical decisions, but for restoring confidence among clinicians, patients, and families in how care is planned before the crisis.

Drawing on over seven years of development and a rare breadth of clinical experience across eight specialties, the author has refined a model of expert-led emergency care planning to address these systemic gaps. A second-cycle audit of this approach demonstrated plan quality and hospital avoidance outcomes exceeding national benchmarks by 2–3x (>70% hospital admission avoidance).

These early results support further investment in evaluation, training, expert certification, and system-wide partnerships — to scale impact across the UK and beyond.

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